

HYPERBOLE AS A TOOL INDEPENDENT OF THE SPEAKER'S INTENTION

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Gibbs advocates a distinction between hyperbole and simple overstatement, by which a person unconsciously or unintentionally expresses a proposition that is stronger than the evidence warrants, whereas hyperbole is fundamentally intentional. Kreuz and Roberts also support this intentional component in defining hyperbole as “deliberate exaggeration”. The obvious difficulty here, as McCarthy and Carter note, is how to operationalize a speaker-internal notion of intention since the same proposition can be overstatement in one person's mouth and hyperbole in another's.

Among the five components of classical rhetoric, elocution, or the artistic use of language, gradually emerged as the major focus of interest, to such an extent as to virtually become a discipline of its own. Essentially, this single division of the classical rhetoric constitutes the field that today we call stylistics. The literary critic, as Turner has noted, has long been concerned with style and artistic creativity, so the debt of modern stylistics to rhetoric is evident and accepted as such. Dubois have even claimed that rhetoric is the knowledge of language procedures characteristic of literature. Thus, literature is always referred to as the paragon of standards, being poets, and in general literary writers, the best guarantors of exemplary usage. Tropes, in particular, have traditionally been treated as poetic tools. Since literary texts gradually became accepted as the most appropriate arena for speaking figuratively, it is not surprising that nowadays figuration is almost exclusively associated with literature.

The assumption that figurative language is exclusively ornamental has a long history in literary criticism. It has long been assumed that figurative language adds a rich aesthetic dimension to speaking and writing. Hence, literary writers employ figures of speech, such as hyperbole, to achieve certain aesthetic effects. It is commonly believed that figurative usage is not conceptually useful, but meant to “beautify prosaic ideas”. Thus, figures of speech are generally viewed as embellishments of ordinary literal language with little cognitive value of their own. In literary studies, the emphasis has been primarily laid on poetic or stylistic devices, as opposed to non-literal language per se. Associated with each literary genre is a distinctive set of aesthetic devices that enhance the aesthetic effect, including figurative language (e.g. irony, metaphor, hyperbole), shifts in perspective (e.g. points of view of narrator and characters, flashbacks) as well as phonological patterns (e.g. rhyme, assonance, alliteration). The type and density of these literary items predict the extent to which texts are regarded as literary. Within this framework, hyperbole primarily becomes a form of ornamentation, which lends beauty and interest to writing. Unfortunately, the idea that figurative language can be interesting or beautiful, as Pollio remark, has come perversely to suggest that such expression is only ornamental and that ornament is neither functional, nor useful. Thus, in literary criticism, hyperbole has been examined as a technique used to compel, ornament or interest, as well as a form of creativity, as the creative expression of some idea. Literary language forces tension on the distinction between form and content. Pollio express this idea in the following terms: For most speaking situations form remains submerged in content: we are usually aware of what is said rather than how it is said. Figurative expression calls attention to the medium itself and in this way forces the listener or reader to pay simultaneous attention to both medium and

message. In good figurative usage form and content fulfil a single intention; in lesser usage one or the other dominates. In all cases, however, it is the tendency of poetic language to demand its due that makes us stop and ponder not only on content, but style, as well as style and content.

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